

The RiverCure Portal and Citizen Science: Usability Assessment Guide

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What is the RiverCure Portal?

The RiverCure Portal (RCP) is a web platform that collects and processes data using hydrodynamic modelling tools, and generates information about flood risk, which can be used in various phases of the risk management cycle for this type of event. Initially developed for specialised users, the RCP now aims to engage citizens in its scientific efforts. Citizens can now use the RCP to contribute relevant observational data regarding these phenomena.

In the Portal, citizens can find and interact with the concepts of Context, Event, Contribution, and Quiz. A Context represents a geographical area of interest. An Event refers to a set of real or simulated occurrences taking place over a specific period within a defined geographical area. A Contribution is a set of information provided by the user concerning a real situation they have observed. Finally, a Quiz consists of a series of questions that users can answer. Quizzes may be linked to an Event, presenting questions related to it, or may be general in nature, aiming to raise awareness.

User Session Goals

The goal of this session is to assess the new functionalities now available, namely the ability for citizens to submit Contributions. Additionally, the current usability of the RiverCure Portal from a citizen's perspective will also be evaluated. This assessment will be conducted through the completion of a series of simple tasks on the Portal.

To carry out this session, a fictional scenario will be used, enabling the user to submit a Contribution. The scenario does not reflect any real event, and the photo provided to accompany the Contribution does not correspond to the geographical location described in the scenario.

An awareness-raising Quiz on tsunamis will also be completed.

At the end of the session, the user will be invited to provide feedback through a brief questionnaire. The resulting observations will offer key and highly valuable insights into the current quality of the platform and will help identify areas for future improvement.

Conditions

- Tasks must be performed without support or help from others;
- Reliable Internet connection and a modern web browser (Google Chrome, Mozilla Firefox, Microsoft Edge, or Safari) must be used;
- The tasks can be carried out on a computer or a mobile phone;
- The session is expected to last around 10 minutes.

Instructions

A – Accessing the RCP

1. Access the RiverCure Portal (RCP) by visiting <http://rivercure.inesc-id.pt:8080/>
2. Create a new user account and then log-in;
3. Change the language of the Portal according to your preference;
4. Take a moment to find out what the RCP is about;
5. Find out how to contact the RCP, if necessary;

B – Contexts and Contributions

6. Take a moment to explore the Homepage;
7. Find Context “Coura-Questionário-Usabilidade” (Tip: if you prefer using the map, it’s near Coura);
8. Find this Context’s details (Tip: if you prefer using the map, click the blue area);
9. Find the list of Events from this Context;
10. In a new tab of your browser, open (URL no longer available) and download the photo, which will be used in the next step;
11. Make a Contribution to Context “Coura-Questionário-Usabilidade”, in which you report having seen a situation with the following details:
 - Flood;
 - 7 of September of 2024;
 - In a location of your choice, within the boundaries of the Context.;
 - Attach the photo obtained in step (10).
12. Take a moment to explore the details of your Contribution and verify that everything is correct;
13. Find the list of Contributions other users have published in this Context;
14. See the details of one Contribution that has been published by another user in this Context;

C – Quizzes

15. Take a moment to explore the Portal's Public Quizzes;
16. Find the details about Quiz "Tsunami em Lisboa" (translates to "Tsunami in Lisbon");
17. Participate in Quiz "Tsunami em Lisboa";
18. Find out if your answers are correct.

To collect your feedback on about completing the tasks above, please fill in the form below:

(Form no longer available)

Thank you for your participation!